

Development of Postal Office Theory

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Abstract:

Post office mail in modern days is similar to e-mail, where sender and receiver are discussed, same like as of unique email address. Thus, in this paper, we shall attempt to study, about postal services for its development and improvement.

Introduction:

While sending letters, parcels, and any things from postal mail, we need postal tickets which are like a sticker. Thus we shall begin with reformulation of postal tickets, by including Patent, Copyrights, as well as insurance, especially for the letters, and inventions, either be mini or micro, based on letters sent. Here is our proposed sample of postal sticker shown in figure below (Fig:a)

Fig:a

In our proposed sample of postal tickets, we have included copyright registration, patent registration, postal ticket's identification number, currency of postal tickets (as per various values), insurance number, and photo of person for whom postal ticket is issued (generally in honor of). All of the identification numbers are unique; except for the currency value, and unique identification is introduced for proper

record-keeping, based on authorities like as Postal Service administration, insurance, copyright registrar, patent registrar; all administrations working with a co-ordination for postal tickets. Thus, in this way, Postal tickets is attempted to be improvised. For letters, that aren't published, postal sticker would ensure security of intellectual property, as well as would allow us to find out, where any postal ticket was used.

That was a brief description about an proposed sample of postal stickers.

Mailing:

Our post mail box, generally just receives, or sends, and when inbox, outbox, and sent are discussed same like as of typical email, we can slightly modify our mail box as shown in figure below (Fig b)

Fig: b

We can find post mail boxes, in certain places, where we can deposit our letters, or can find post mail box from where we can send our letters. In the above sample of post mail box, a box is divided into two halves; one for sending letters, and another for receiving letters. It would be same like as of inbox, and outbox, until post-man would come and receive the letter, to make it like as "sent" in email system. Using sensors to alert post office, and individuals, in post mail box would add glamour to the postmail box, as post office would be alerted, whenever we would need send our letters, and we would be alerted, whenever we would need to receive our letters, after any letters gets inserted in post mail box.

Online Transactions and Mailing:

Postal ticket, as per its value of currency, would need to be digitalized, same like as general currency notes and monetary policies. When postal tickets too is digitalized, then the postal tickets of certain amount would be equivalent to the currency amount of same value. That would need general banking procedures and exchanges, to exchange, deposit or withdraw, having features as discussed in sample postal ticket above.

In case of Nepal:

In Nepal, application letters in many of purposes require postal ticket of certain currency value, and when online transactions are studied for postal services, then, developing a submission manager would be best, to submit/send any application letter, to concerned person/ authority, by means of online post mail system. By means of submission manager, that can scan and digitalized even hand-written application to photograph or even in printed form would add further glamour. Use of mobile wallets [1], can be done, to buy postal tickets online, then use that postal ticket in application, with all facilities for securing intellectual property, by means of online postal sticker.

Conclusion:

Thus, by means of digitalized as well as non-digitalized postal tickets, not only intellectual property can be made secured, but even their transactions can be done, and postal address would still continue to serve as an address.

References

1. Arjun Dahal. (2021). Digital Currencies and Transactions at Glance. Zenodo.
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